

FIRST AID IN EMERGENCY SITUATIONS

Mambetkarimov Berdax Biysenbaevich

Inspector of the Emergency Management Training Center of the Republic of
Karakalpakstan

mambetkarimovberdax 23@gcom

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Resolution №600 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 14.10.2022 "On Measures to Implement the Constitutional Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on State of Emergency" was adopted. Based on this, persons who have reached the age of 18 and are able to work according to their knowledge, skills and health can be involved in the work in the area where the state of emergency has been introduced. It is prohibited to attract the following persons: persons with disabilities of the first and second groups and their caregivers; disabled persons; pregnant women; persons raising a child with the first and second group of disabilities; One of the parents or guardian of a child under 12 years of age; Women under 35 years old.

First aid is necessary for every person in emergency situations. Solving the problems of prolonging the life of every person, maintaining and strengthening his health is an important task of the health sector. In our country, these issues are implemented through continuous improvement of the organizational forms of treatment and prevention assistance, including emergency medical assistance to the population. The correct organization of health issues comes from the integral connection between theory and practice, that is, it is closely related to the practical implementation of the achievements of modern medical science [1]. Timely first aid often becomes a decisive factor in saving the lives of injured and sick people in

accidents and sudden illnesses. At least it has a significant positive effect in preventing the duration of the disease, temporary incapacity for work and disability. Emergency medical care is of great importance in the event of an accident or sudden illness. But even the most well-organized medical treatment can be ineffective and delayed if the injured person is not provided with the necessary first aid in time. Because in all accidents, the injury is sudden and life-threatening. The result of the injury, especially in severe and dangerous injuries, is resolved in the first minutes. That is why the ability of the person at the scene of an accident to provide quick and effective first aid is very important and vital. In addition, it is necessary to be very careful in providing first aid. Because you can cause further damage to the person you are trying to help. It is important to remember that your support is only the beginning of treatment. No matter how necessary it is, it can never replace the competent approach of a medical specialist. Your task is not to treat the injured, but only to provide first aid. In order to provide first aid quickly and qualitatively, you need to have special knowledge.

The most common peacetime accidents include mechanical injury, burns, heat and sunstroke, frostbite and general frostbite, suffocation due to drowning and grounding, carbon monoxide poisoning, electric shock, and lightning. In these cases, the main tasks of first aid are to save the life of the injured with the most necessary measures, to reduce their suffering, to prevent possible complications, and to ease the course of illness and injury [2].

First aid is provided at the scene of the accident by the injured person himself (self-aid) or by another person (mutual aid) and by specially trained persons.

In providing first aid, it is necessary to quickly identify the source (factor) of the injury, remove it, apply medical aid measures recommended for each injury, call a doctor or take the injured person to the nearest medical facility. In some cases (heavy bleeding, severe bone fractures, loss of consciousness, respiratory and

cardiac arrest, etc.), it is absolutely impossible to transport (transport) the injured without first providing emergency medical care on the spot.

In such cases, resuscitation measures are necessary. Reanimation (resuscitation) is a set of immediate measures aimed at bringing a dying person back to life and preventing irreversible changes in his organs and tissues. First of all, it is achieved to restore and maintain breathing and blood circulation of the injured.

Uncomplicated measures of resuscitation (artificial respiration, indirect heart massage) are known to everyone. In addition, in most cases, injured people need help that everyone can do, such as stopping bleeding, relieving pain, immobilizing a broken limb, and protecting wounds, burns, and frostbite from infection.

First aid should be provided as soon as possible after the accident. In cases of severe bleeding, electric shock, drowning, suffocation, cardiac arrest, and other cases, first aid should be provided immediately without delay. If several people are injured at the same time, the duration and sequence of assistance will be determined.

First aid is given to children and people in need of urgent care. The sequence of measures to be taken in providing first aid to people with multiple and additional injuries should be determined. First, the procedures that allow to save the life of the injured person or are necessary for the application of further measures of first aid are carried out. For example, in the case of an open fracture of the femur and bleeding from the artery, it is necessary to first stop the life-threatening bleeding, then apply a sterile bandage to the wound, and only then begin to immobilize the leg. In order to immobilize the fractured area, you need to use a special bandage or other tools at hand [3].

All methods of first aid should be performed with care and caution. If rough actions are taken, it can harm the injured person and make his condition worse. If first aid is provided by not one, but two or more people, then it is necessary to

work together. One of the assistants is the chief, who should be in charge of all the procedures of first aid.

In the conditions of first aid, the issue of diagnosis is of great importance. Because a timely and correct diagnosis makes it possible to determine the type of illness or injury and to draw up a plan for the sequence of necessary assistance measures on this basis.

The diagnosis is based on the determination of subjective and objective symptoms of the disease or injury.

Subjective signs include the complaints of the patient or injured person (if he is conscious).

Objective signs include external signs of illness and injury or determined by a certain methodological approach, for example, measuring the pulse (pulse), the amount of breathing and exhalation, reflexes and other signs.

Objective and subjective symptoms of a disease or injury can be general or specific for this condition. Thanks to this, it is possible to make a preliminary diagnosis by identifying and providing these signs. Based on the diagnosis, the type of help needed is also determined.

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